

MICROBIOLOGICAL ANALYSIS OF WATER IN THE CANAL DANUBE-TISA-DANUBE

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SUMMARY: Contaminated water has a very negative impact on the entire agroecosystem. Surface water is usually polluted through the discharge of pollutants of various origins such as wastewater from industries and households, wastewater from livestock, washing harmful chemicals from the soil into the groundwater, oil spills and more. In this water, there are a variety of harmful and toxic substances, as well as pathogenic microorganisms. The consequences can be disastrous and large-scale. One way of removing unwanted and harmful substances from the wastewater is biological. Biological control means separation of harmful substances through the metabolism of microorganisms. The aim of this work was to estimate the microbiological quality of water in the canal Danube-Tisa-Danube (DTD) at two different locations and the possibility of using this water in agricultural production. Water samples for microbiological analysis were taken from one locality near the village Čelarevo, and two localities near Vrbas, outside of direct influence of wastewater flows and its tributaries. Water samples were taken according to the guidelines for taking samples of surface water from rivers and streams ISO 5667-6. Time up period was from January to June 2013. Each sample containing 100ml of water was transferred in the laboratory. Microbiological analysis included the determination of total number of bacteria, the number of Salmonella sp., Echerichia coli and the number of sulphite reducing clostridia (genus Clostridia). Large number of saprophytic bacteria as well as the fluorescent Pseudomonas sp. were found at both localities in the investigated time period.

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The number of Salmonella spp. and E. coli was high indicating the presence of water pollution. Sulphite reducing clostridia were recorded in small numbers, only at the end of the test period, which points to a lack of anaerobic conditions in the canal water. The presented results suggest that the water from the tested localities need to be treated before it is used in agricultural purpose.

Key words: *Salmonella sp., Echerichia coli, Clostridia sp., water, canal Danube-Tisa-Danube.*

INTRODUCTION

Contaminated water have a very negative impact on the entire agroecosystem. Surface water is usually polluted through the discharge of pollutants of various origins such as wastewater from industries and households, wastewater from livestock, washing harmful chemicals from the soil into the groundwater and more. Also, the anthropogenic factor has a significant impact on water pollution, throwing various types of waste into the water (Fan et al., 2009; Sapers et al., 2009). Consequences can be disastrous and large-scale. In contaminated water there are a variety of hazardous and toxic materials, substances and pathogenic microorganisms. The list of pathogens includes bacteria *Campylobacter sp.*, enterohemorrhagic *Escherichia coli*, enterotoxigenic *Staphylococcus aureus*, enterotoxigenic *Bacillus cereus*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Salmonella sp.*, *Shigella sp.*, *Yersinia enterocolitica*, protozoa *Cryptosporidium sp.*, *Cyclospora cayetanensis*, *Giardia sp.*, *Entamoeba histolytica*, and viruses, in particular, adenoviruses, enteroviruses, noroviruses, and rotaviruses (Warriner et al., 2009).

Because of the wastewater negative effects, it is necessary to invest a lot of effort to protect the environment. One way of removing harmful substances from the wastewater is bioremediation. Bioremediation is an alternative method that has emerged in recent years to treat the wastewater. The applications of microorganisms, such as bacteria, fungi, algae, dead microbial biomass and other biomaterials, are the hot topics in this research realm (Cabatingan et al., 2009; Bingol, et al. 2004; Aravindhnan et al., 2004).

In our country, the sanitary quality of irrigation water sources is unknown currently. Therefore, the objective of this work was to estimate the microbiological quality of water in the canal Danube-Tisa-Danube (DTD) at two differant locations and the possibility of using this water in agricultural production.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Water samples for microbiological analysis were taken from one locality near the village Čelarevo, and two lokalities near Vrbas, outside of direct influence of wastewater flows and its tributaries. Water samples were taken according to the guidelines for taking samples of surface water from rivers and streams ISO 5667-6. Sampling period was from January to June 2013.

Each sample containing 100 ml of water was transferred in the laboratory. Microbiological analysis included the determination of total number of bacteria, the number of *Salmonella sp.*, *Echerichia coli* and the number of sulphite reducing clostridia (genus *Clostridia*). The number of microorganisms was determined, using the dilution method (Trolldenier, 1996). Appropriate nutrient media were used: nutrient agar for the total number of bacteria, HiCrome Salmonella agar for the number of *Salmonella sp.* and *Echerichia coli*, and medium with pepton (pepton 15 g l⁻¹, extract yeast 9 g l⁻¹, NaSO₃ 0.5 g l⁻¹, agar 15 g l⁻¹; after medium sterilization, 20 ml of 7% solution of FeSO₄ was added) for the sulphite reducing clostridia.

Graphically displayed results are presented as logarithm of cell number.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Saprophytic bacteria play an important role in the process of water purification. In this study, the number of saprophytic bacteria during the six months of testing at all three sites was very high. The highest number was recorded in May at the site Vrbas 1 and it was 15.97×10^5 CFU/ml, while the minimum was in March at the site Vrbas 2, 0.26×10^5 CFU/ml (Graf 1). Also, in the water samples at locality Vrbas 1, colonies of fluorescent *Pseudomonas sp.* were identified. These bacteria have capability to use a variety of pollutants as a source of nutrients.

Graph.1. Number of saprophytic bacteria in the water of canal DTD from January to June 2013th (cells number logarithm)

The results obtained for the site Čelarevo show that the largest number of bacteria in the water was in January and February, and then decreased. In the spring months, it was noted a slight increase in the number of saprophytic bacteria. The number of saprophytic bacteria was high during winter months although the water temperature was at border of the minimum for survival of these bacteria. It could be explained by the increased influx of organic matter in the water of canal DTD. At sites Vrbas 1 and 2 number of bacteria decreased from winter to spring, and reached its peak in May.

Escherichia coli inhabits the intestines of animals, as well as humans, where is intensively involved in the process of digestion. This bacterium causes many human diseases such as diarrhea, urogenital tract infection, sepsis and other. It also serves as an indicator of water quality (McLain and Williams, 2008; Higgins et al., 2009). The presence of enterobacteria *E. coli* in the water of canal DTD at all locations during the six month, indicates the flow of raw sewage into the water canal, while a relatively high abundance of this bacteria indicates a large contamination of the canal (Graph. 2). The largest number of *E. coli* was recorded at the site Vrbas 2 in June, and it was $2,80 \times 10^3$ CFU/ml. Contrary to that, no presence of the bacteria was determined in the canal water at the same site in February.

Graph. 2. Number of *Escherichia coli* in the water channel DTD from January to June 2013th (cells number logarithm)

The above graph shows that the numbers of *E. coli* during the winter months, January and February, were lower than in the spring and summer months. The highest number was recorded in June. This trend in the number of *E. coli* in the water during the examined period can be explained by the growth of optimal temperature for this bacteria which is 37°C.

Salmonella sp. is the causative agent of various diseases in the human. It causes infection of the gastrointestinal tract or salmonellosis, thyroid and parathyroid fever and also food poisoning. The number of *Salmonella* sp. in the canal on the three examined sites was relatively low (Graph. 3). The highest number was recorded in March at the site near the Vrbas 1 and it was 560 cells per ml. Also, there were periods when this bacterium was not identified.

Graph. 3. Number of *Salmonella* sp. in the water of canal DID from January to June 2013th (cells number logarithm)

Bacteria of the *Clostridium* genus are anaerobic, Gram-positive, rod-shaped, endospore-forming bacteria. Causing a variety of diseases in humans such as gas gangrene, botulism, sepsis and etc., bacteria from the *Clostridium* genera are commonly present in natural environment, e.g. they live in dust, soil, water, bottom sediments and in human and animal alimentary canals (Moriishi et al., 1996). Species of the genus *Clostridium* can synthesize strong exotoxins which can be lethal to humans and animals (Beckers et al., 2010). The total number of sulphite reducing clostridia in the water of canal DTD, at the tested sites was very low (Graf 4). The highest number was found in May at the site Vrbas 1.

Graph. 4. Number of *Clostridium* spp. in the water of canal DID (cells number logarithm)

According to Matavuly et al. (2003), the water of DTD canal at almost all tested localities belonged to slightly polluted waters, II class according to Kohl (1975). Few exceptions were recorded in the spring season when water quality were categorized as polluted - III class.

On the basis of the results of our research, it can be concluded that the water from the tested localities need to be treated before it is used in agricultural purpose.

CONCLUSION

A large number of saprophytic bacteria and the presence of the fluorescent *Pseudomonas* sp. indicates the presence of large amounts of organic matter in the water of canal DTD which is probably due to contamination. The number of *Salmonella* sp. and *Escherichia coli* is also high, especially in the spring months (April, May, June), which is also evidence of water pollution. A small number of sulphite reducing clostridia in water and only at the end of the test period, suggests a lack of anaerobic conditions in the water of canal DTD. Results presented in this paper suggest that the water in the canal DTD near Vrbas and Čelarevo should be remediate and purify before using in agricultural purposes.

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MIKROBIOLOŠKI SASTAV VODE KANALA DUNAV-TISA-DUNAV

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Izvod

Zagađene vode imaju vrlo negativan uticaj na celokupan agroekosistem. Zagađivanje površinskih voda najčešće se vrši putem ispuštanja zagađujućih materija različitog porekla kao što su otpadne vode iz industrija i domaćinstava, otpadne vode sa stočnih farmi, ispiranjem štetnih hemijskih materija iz zemljišta u podzemne vode, izlivanjem nafte i drugo. Posledice mogu biti katastrofalne i velikih razmera. Jedan od načina da se uklone štetne materije iz otpadnih voda jeste biološkim putem. Cilj ovog rada je da se na osnovu mikrobiološkog kvaliteta vode kanala DTD, na dva različita lokaliteta, proceni mogućnost upotrebe te vode, u okviru poljoprivredne proizvodnje. Uzorci vode za mikrobiološke analize uzeti su iz kanala DTD sa jednog lokaliteta kod naselja Čelarevo, i sa dva lokaliteta kod Vrbasa, van zone direktnog uticaja uliva otpadnih voda i pritoka. Uzorci vode uzimani su prema smernicama za uzimanje uzoraka površinskih voda iz reka i potoka SRPSISO 5667-6. Vremenski period praćenja bio je od januara do juna 2013. godine. Po 100 ml svakog uzorka vode donešeni su u laboratoriju gde su vršene mikrobiološke analize na ukupan broj bakterija, broj roda *Salmonella* sp., vrste *E. coli* i zastupljenosti sulfid redukujućih klostridija (rod *Clostridium* sp.). Na oba lokaliteta zabeležen je velik broj saprofitnih bakterija i prisustvo fluorescirajućih *Pseudomonas* sp. Ovi podaci ukazuju na prisustvo velike količine organske materije u vodi kanala, što je verovatno posledica zagađenja. Brojnost roda *Salmonella* sp. i vrste *E. coli* je takođe visoka, naročito u prolećnim mesecima, što je takođe dokaz prisutnog zagađenja vode. Sulfid redukujuće klostridije su u vodi registrovane u malom broju i samo na kraju ispitivanog perioda, što ukazuje na odsustvo isključivih anaerobnih uslova u vodi kanala DTD. U pogledu korišćenja vode kanala DTD u poljoprivredne svrhe, voda sa ispitivanih lokaliteta morala bi se prethodno prečistiti na šta upućuju izneti rezultati.

Ključne reči: *Salmonella* sp., *E. coli*, *Clostridia* sp., voda, kanal Dunav-Tisa-Dunav.

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